

Infra-Red Spectra of Metal-Thiourea Complexes

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The infra-red spectra of urea complexes were studied¹ to determine whether co-ordination occurs through nitrogen or oxygen. From infra-red studies on thiourea complexes, Yamaguchi *et al.*² found that the metals Pt, Pd, Zn and Ni form M-S bonds since, as for the M-O bonds in urea complexes, the C-N stretching frequency increases and the C-S stretching frequency decreases upon coordination without appreciable change of the N-H stretching frequency. More recently, the I. R. absorption spectra of thiourea complexes of some more metals, like Co, Mn, Cu, Hg, Cd and Pb were reported³ and the results were interpreted to show the existence of metal to sulphur bond rather than metal to nitrogen bond. The infra-red spectra of several metal-thiourea complexes of manganese (II), iron (II), cobalt (II) and mercury (II) are reported in this communication; spectra of some of the compounds investigated by others³ have been reinvestigated for comparison and the existence of metal-sulphur bond has been established in all the cases.

The thiourea complexes were prepared by the methods reported earlier⁴⁻⁷. The spectra were recorded in Nujol mulls on a Unicam SP200 double beam spectrophotometer with rock salt optics in the range 5000-650 cm^{-1} . The relevant data are recorded in table I.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It has been well established⁸ that in thiourea, there are almost equal contributions from the canonical forms I, II and III.

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If bonding takes place through sulphur, the contribution from the forms II and III will increase and this decreases the bond order of the carbon-sulphur link towards the value for a single bond whilst that of the carbon-nitrogen bond approaches the value for a double bond. Hence in such complexes, the C-S stretching frequency should decrease and that of C-N should increase. If on the other hand the metal is bonded through nitrogen but not sulphur, just the opposite effect will be expected.

TABLE I
Infra-Red absorption bands of metal-thiourea complexes

tu	740 (s)	1095 (s)	1420 (s)	(1476)	1610 (s)		
Mntu ₄ Cl ₂	722 (sh)	735 (s)	1105 (m)	1400 (sh)		1610 (br-st)	1625 (sh)
Cotu ₄ Cl ₂	722 (sh)	735 (s)	1105 (w)			1600 (br-st)	1625 (sh)
Nitu ₄ Cl ₂	728 (s)		1100 (m)	1460 (sh)	1490 (s)	1600 (br-st)	
Fctu ₄ Cl ₂	720 (sh)	738 (s)	1100 (br)			1600 (br-st)	
Mntu ₄ Br ₂	720 (sh)	740 (s)	1100 (br)			1600 (br-st)	1625 (sh)
Cotu ₄ Br ₂	720 (s)			1430 (s)	1505(w)	1620 (br-st)	
Cotu ₄ I ₂	715 (s)	745 (s)					
Cotu ₃ Cl ₃	725 (sh)	735 (s)	1100 (w)			1600 (br-st)	1625 (w)
Cotu ₃ Br ₃	712 (s)			1430(s)	1505(m)	1620 (br-st)	
Cotu ₄ Cl ₂	720 (s)	740 (sh)	1100 (s)	1490 (sh)	1510 (sh)	1620 (br)	
Cotu ₂ Br ₂	718 (s)	725 (sh)				1620 (br-st)	
Cotu ₂ I ₂	718 (s)	725 (sh)					
Hg tu ₂ Cl ₂	728 (m)	740 (s)	1120 (s)	1412 (m)	1508 (s)	1618 (br-st)	1650 (s)
Hg ₂ tu ₂ Cl ₄	718 (s)	740 (s)	1120 (s)	1425 (w)	1518 (w)	1630 (s)	

s-sharp, m-medium, w-weak, sh-shoulder, br-broad, st-strong, tu-thiourea.

There was difference of opinion in the assignment of absorption bands at about 730 cm^{-1} and 1086 cm^{-1} . It was argued that the absorption band at 730 cm^{-1} (740 cm^{-1} in the present work) was primarily due to C-S stretching and this was shifted consistently to a lower frequency on forming metal sulphur bonds⁹. The results reported now also exhibit this behaviour. In most of the cases, the band at 740 cm^{-1} is split and shifted to a lower frequency (table I) indicating a M-S bonding. Olliff⁹ also reported a similar shift of this band to a lower frequency from 733 to 718 cm^{-1} in case of Nitu₄Cl₂.

The absorption at 1086 cm^{-1} (1095 cm^{-1} in the present work) was attributed^{9,10} to NH₂ rocking modes and not to C-S stretching as postulated earlier⁹. As such, this is not expected to be affected by the formation of a metal-sulphur bond and the results obtained now are consistent with this observation except in case of mercury complexes. The band found by earlier workers^{9,10}, at 1476 cm^{-1} in free thiourea representing the N-C-N stretching mode could not be noticed by us since Nujol absorbs heavily at 1475 cm^{-1} . They studied the samples as KBr discs but not as Nujol mulls. This band is expected to be sensitive to coordination through sulphur and is to be shifted to higher frequency regions because of the increased double bond character of the C-N bond. In case of Nitu₄Cl₂, Olliff⁹ noticed a shift to 1500 cm^{-1} similar to our value of 1490 cm^{-1} . The shift to a higher

9. Olliff, R. W., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2037.

10. Stewart, J. E., *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, 26, 248.

frequency was noticed by us also in case of mercury and some cobalt complexes but in other cases where the shift is not much, it has been overlapped by Nujol peak. The absorption bands at about 1420 and 1610 cm^{-1} are split in some cases and this behaviour is similar to the one noticed earlier³.

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